

ISic0078

I.Sicily inscription 0078

Language

Punic

Type

dedication (?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644813

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.11

Garbini, G 1967. Catalogo delle iscrizioni fenicie conservate nel Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Palermo. *Kokalos*. 13: 66-72. At 67 no.2 fig.12.1

Garbini, G 1965. Note di epigrafia punica I. *Rivista degli Studi Orientali*. 40: 205-213. At 206-210 tav.2

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